

1
2 **Querying the Past—Using Artificial**
3 **Intelligence to Identify Architecture**

4
5 Pattee Aaron*¹, Kröber Cindy ², Brusckke Jonas ³, Utescher
6 Ronja ⁴, Maiwald Ferdinand ², Zarriß Sina ⁴, Hoppe Stephan ¹,
7 Niebling Florian ³, Münster Sander ²

8
9 ¹*Ludwig-Maximilians-University in Munich*

10 ²*Friedrich-Schiller-University in Jena*

11 ³*Julius-Maximilian-University in Würzburg*

12 ⁴*University of Bielefeld*

13
14 *Corresponding author

15 Correspondence: acpattee30@gmail.com

16
17 **ABSTRACT**

18 This paper presents the current state of the HistKI (Historical Artificial Intelligence) project that seeks
19 to combine image and text data with 3D models in a 4D search engine. The goal of the project is to
20 provide a robust tool for art historians and archaeologists researching the development architecture
21 and dissemination of architectural features. The case study of Dresden, Germany, and its 18th century
22 baroque palatial complex, known as the Zwinger, is well suited for modern research of architecture as
23 it combines numerous visual data with textual contexts consisting of histories and social networks of
24 both the buildings and their architects. The relevance of such a project is substantiated by the current
25 war in Ukraine. Considering that the baroque history of Ukraine shares much in common with the
26 Saxon architecture of the 18th century, the 4D browser presented in the paper can provide an example
27 to be replicated, allowing researchers to identify precisely where destroyed buildings were within
28 their suburban contexts, but also to research the architectural networks that brought them about.

29 **Keywords:** Artificial Intelligence in 3D space, Machine Learning, Architectural History

30

32 The studies of archaeology and architectural art history have greatly benefitted from innovative,
33 computer-aided approaches in recent years. From high resolution 2D photos of building edifices, to 3D
34 models of entire structures, these emerging techniques are laying the foundation for new methodologies
35 in researching architecture. Provided the three-dimensional nature of buildings, research projects have
36 appropriately focused upon techniques that produce digital replicas of their forms, such as *Structure from*
37 *Motion* (SfM) Photogrammetry and *Terrestrial Laser Scanning* (TLS). However, one critical aspect in the
38 study of architecture has largely been dormant since the emergence of these technologies, namely, the
39 computer-aided description of architectural elements. Although *Artificial Intelligence* (AI)-based
40 methodologies have been tremendously developed in recent years within the field of *Computer Vision*, it
41 has served a more marginal role with regard to image searches in repositories and retrieval systems.
42 Current processes within Computer Vision extract purely visual features within images of related sources,
43 which are then classified based upon these characteristics alone. Unfortunately, key contextual data in the
44 form of text or metadata are not linked to the images. This project seeks to establish an AI-based approach
45 towards modelling image sources and their multimodal contexts as a new technique for researchers in the
46 Humanities. Using a city model of Dresden, Germany, as our main case study, we will demonstrate how we
47 are using AI to identify architectural elements directly from 3D models rather than rely upon text
48 descriptors.

49

50 1.1 Historical Background and Modern Relevance

51

52 The prevalence of highly destructive war tactics over the course of the last century has erased vast
53 swaths of built cultural heritage. Just as the horrific shadow of the Second World War was entering its final
54 stages of fading into the past, conventional warfare made a violent resurgence with Russia's invasion of
55 Ukraine. Typically, the study of destroyed European cities was the domain of archaeologists and
56 architectural historians, though now it includes journalists and essentially everyone else. Artillery strikes,
57 indiscriminate bombings, missile attacks, and small arms fire have once again left a European country in
58 shambles with some of its cities no longer recognizable. It is for this reason, that the selection of Dresden
59 as our case study is particularly suited to the modern day. Itself indiscriminately fire-bombed into oblivion,
60 the ruins of the city of Dresden were rehabilitated or even removed during 40 years of communism. After
61 the re-unification of Germany, Dresden received a remarkable surge of funding to repair its crumbling
62 infrastructure and even rebuild its old city. The reconstructions are not merely facades or the occasional
63 statue. These reconstructions include the entire palatial grounds and residence of the Saxon rulers who
64 had been previously been Electors of the Holy Roman Empire and the Kings of Poland during the Great
65 Northern War of 1700 -1721. The Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth that fell to the charge of the Saxon
66 Elector, August II, encompassed much of what is currently western Ukraine, including the city of Lviv and
67 as far south as Bratslav in south-central Ukraine. These territories passed to August II's son, August III, after
68 his death with the help of Anna of Russia. The Russian Empire had included much of Eastern Ukraine and
69 had been a key ally of the Saxons against the Swedes and Ottomans. This central bulwark against their
70 northern and southern aggressors resulted in a political alliance that also culturally linked the two via
71 architecture (Gurlitt, 1924). The second version of the Winter Palace in St. Petersburg was built under the
72 architect Georg Mattarnovi, a former student of the architect Andreas Schlüter who built the Royal Palace
73 of Berlin and the Amber Room of Tsarskoye Selo near St. Petersburg (Hendel, 1719; Nicolai, n.d.). Both
74 Mattarnovi and Schlüter were from Prussia and worked in the Commonwealth of Poland-Lithuania before
75 and after it passed to Saxon hands. In fact, Prussia completed the trifecta as an ally of Saxony and Russia.

76

77 Upon his accession, August III of Saxony continued the building projects of his predecessors both in
78 Saxony and in the commonwealth lands through the office of the Saxon *Oberlandbaumeister* (chief
79 architect). This officer of the court was not only in charge of palatial building projects, but also of military
80 bastions for artillery positions in times of war. The apotheosis of the position was the great Wolf Caspar
81 von Klengel who set the standard for his successors in that office who incorporated his architectural designs
82 into their own (Passavant, 2001). Most notably, this included Matthäus Daniel Pöppelmann—chief
83 architect in the court of August II—who constructed the grand Zwinger in Dresden connected to the
84 Residence that had been renovated by Klengel. Pöppelmann was even chief architect while the Morsztyn
85 Palace was being rebuilt as the new Saxon Palace of Warsaw by Kings August II and August III (Heckmann,
86 1986). Sadly, this grand palace was demolished by German forces in WWII. However, it was not only grand
87 palaces that were built by these architects and their networks, but smaller city palaces as well such as the
88 Taschenbergpalais in Dresden by Pöppelmann or the Lelewel Palace in Warsaw by Ephraim Schröger
89 (Hendel, n.d.)—both of which were painted by the great Venetian artist Bernardo Bellotto (Canaletto).
90 Thus, a tremendous network of architects and artists extended from Dresden into Eastern Poland and
91 Western Ukraine. Many 18th century country manors and palaces were abandoned following the collapse
92 of the Russian Empire, some were repurposed, and others simply demolished—the same phenomenon
93 exhibited in Eastern German after WWII. Unfortunately, many sites in Poland and Western Ukraine have
94 not been investigated and some may fall victim to yet another conventional war. The necessity of an
95 automated system for identifying European baroque architecture is therefore extremely pressing.

96

97

Methods

98 The desire to actively interconnect different data types in order to support new architectural insights
99 and discover historical phenomena is the driving force in this project. The use of a standardized ontology
100 for linking text annotations of architecture to images provided the framework to achieve this goal. Detailed
101 building models within the 3D city model are annotated according to Getty's *Art & Architecture Thesaurus*
102 (AAT) and Wikidata's entity identification numbers (WikiID). The WikiIDs are valid for several languages
103 and therefore lay the foundation for a multilingual interface which will possibly be added later on. Both
104 AAT and WikiIDs were tested to see how well they align with the textual documents of the project. Some
105 relevant terms are currently missing on either one or both lists and need to be added. However, the
106 majority and most relevant terms are included.

107

2.1 Compiling a List of Terms

109

110 The terms themselves are extracted from 35 scholarly sources regarding architecture in Dresden
111 ranging from 19th century reports to recent documentations of the 3D model of the Zwinger. Although the
112 corpus of material includes dozens of sources, only a handful were selected as the basis for the
113 architectural thesaurus. These sources are the most complete of the corpus, as they not only address the
114 architecture using terminology specific to the baroque period, but also explore the architects and their
115 networks. The socio-historical context is critical in understanding the architecture and its development, as
116 monuments are best understood within their own context.

117 The resulting thesaurus includes terms predominately from four sources (Asche, 1966; Heckmann,
118 1979; Jahn et al., 2016; Pfeiffer, 1938), spanning 263 words. This list was achieved by running a Tesseract
119 OCR Pipeline using the *Nopaque* website (<https://nopaque.uni-bielefeld.de/>) hosted by the University of

120 Bielefeld. This free software allows users to select from 17 languages from pdf documents or image files.
121 In total, we submitted over 1000 pages of scholarly material, most of which was originally written in
122 German. After conducting OCR, the texts were put in the free online text analysis software, *Voyant*
123 (<https://voyant-tools.org/>), in order to automatically produce lists of word occurrences from which we
124 could then assemble a master list from the four sources. Once the master list was made, we then post-
125 processed and ‘cleaned’ the list using *OpenRefine* (<https://openrefine.org/>), checking for redundancies and
126 automatically linking the AAT and Wiki IDs to the appropriate term. While this process was on-going, we
127 developed a list of palaces exhibiting similar architecture as the Zwinger and Residence in Dresden from
128 the turn of the 18th century. This palaces list consists of 432 sites identified using WikiData from which we
129 could scrape the internet for images regarding those specific sites. A more detailed explanation of the
130 process was presented in Lausanne, Switzerland, in June 2022 (Utescher et al., 2022) for which an article
131 will soon be published. This provided a broad basis of baroque architecture that could be queried with
132 regard to the results from the sites in Dresden, thus allowing one to use machine learning to make
133 connections between sites across Europe, and more specifically, across Eastern Europe.

134 **2.2 Images and Models in the 4D Browser**

135

136 The images and models of the case study are gathered from multiple online image repositories as well
137 as previous investigations of the site in recent years. The result is a browser consisting of tens of thousands
138 of images that are automatically orientated in the position in which they were taken, including geographical
139 information across time (<https://4dbrowser.urbanhistory4d.org/>). This process works not only for photos
140 of the past ten years, but for historical images as far back as the late 19th century as well. A more detailed
141 report of this process was published in the ISPRS Journal in June of 2023 (Bruschke et al., 2023).

142 In the next step, the images of Dresden will be annotated automatically, by segmenting them using
143 edge detection and feature recognition. However, the already reconstructed camera positions of the
144 images (Maiwald et al., 2021) may also be used to project an image onto the 3D city model (**Figure 1**). This
145 can be used to segment the image and apply the annotated terms to an image section. Tests with the data
146 will show how successful this approach is since the data is very heterogeneous concerning image resolution
147 and level of detail of the models. In a last step the image and texts will be interlinked. This will be done
148 using adapted artificial intelligence approaches (AI) like e.g., CLIP (Contrastive Language-Image Pre-
149 Training).

150

151

152

Figure 1 - Matching of an image and the 3D city model

153

154

155

156

157

158

159

160

To further elaborate on the tasks necessary, it will start with the narrowing down to a certain timespan and area within the 3D model. A filtering using the search bar will only display images and texts referring to the desired feature. From there, it is possible to discover relevant information that do not correspond with the searched term. The links between images and texts will help to close this gap. On the one hand it is possible to visually evaluate an image for relevance and see which sections of text are related, and on the other hand, one can scan the textual documents for connected topics and examine the linked images for a visual clarification or contextualization.

161

Results

162

163

164

165

166

167

168

169

All of the methods funnel into the development of the 4D Browser in which the images, models, maps, and annotations are unified into a cohesive search engine. The browser is freely accessible and was recently tested on a group of art history student in July of 2023 at the *Ludwig-Maximilians-University* (LMU) of Munich, Germany. The students were given the task of exploring the browser for specific networks of architects—as the course was dedicated to networks of architects and their various works. It was very successful and all of the students praised the interactive nature of the browser, finding it to be a very hands-on approach to explore digital humanities. In fact, one student was inspired to change their current direction pursue this area of study instead.

170

171

172

173

174

175

176

177

Regarding the professional application of the browser for architectural research, a group of scholars in Munich and Dresden are already actively using it to buttress their research in baroque architecture. A particular strength of the browser is the ability to explore architecture across time, as it includes a time scroll bar featuring four geo-referenced maps from 1849, 1911, 1967, and 1994. The four maps encompass the rather rapid change that the city has undergone in the past 200 years and thus provide critical geographical and cultural context. The various architects of the 18th century who worked at the palatial complex are also linked in the browser allowing one to discover their involvement in the development of the Saxon baroque style that permeated its way through Eastern Europe.

178

Discussion

179 The key application of this project is to be able to browse hundreds of photos for specific architectural
180 features in order to assist in compiling research on a certain site. For example, identifying certain types of
181 columns exhibited on a building that compare to another building in question. Rather than manually search
182 related buildings based upon one's previous knowledge, the process is aided by using AI to search across a
183 much vaster collection of data. This will greatly enhance the ability of architectural historians and
184 archaeologists alike to compile research and make connections between stylistic phenomena that may
185 have been overlooked. As the browser also makes use of historical photos that are automatically orientated
186 to the position in which they were originally taken, the potential of digitally reconstructing destroyed cities
187 becomes a reality.

188

189

190

Acknowledgements

191 We extend our gratitude to our host universities as well as the TU Dresden, the Saxon State University
192 Library in Dresden (SLUB) and Deutsche Fotothek, as well as all student assistants who have helped develop
193 the 4D Browser.

194

Conflict of interest disclosure

195 The authors declare that they comply with the PCI rule of having no financial conflicts of interest in
196 relation to the content of the article.

197

Funding

198 Full funding is provided by the German Ministry for Education and Research (BMBF) in the category of
199 Digital Humanities (grant ID: 01UG2120)

200

References

- 201 Asche, S. (1966). *Balthasar Permoser und die Barockskulptur des Dresdner Zwingers*. Verlag Weidlich.
- 202 Brusckke, J., Kröber, C., Maiwald, F., Utescher, R., & Pattee, A. (2023). INTRODUCING A MULTIMODAL
203 DATASET FOR THE RESEARCH OF ARCHITECTURAL ELEMENTS. *The International Archives of the*
204 *Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences, XLVIII-M-2–2023*, 325–331.
205 <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLVIII-M-2-2023-325-2023>
- 206 Gurlitt, C. (1924). *August der Starke—Ein Fürstenleben aus der Zeit des deutschen Barock* (2nd ed., Vol. 1).
207 Sibyllen-Verlag.
- 208 Heckmann, H. (1979). *Baumeister des Barock und Rokoko in Sachsen*. Verlag für Bauwesen.
- 209 Heckmann, H. (1986). *Matthäus Daniel Pöppelmann und die Barockbaukunst in Dresden*. Deutsche Verlags-
210 Anstalt.
- 211 Hendel, archINFORM-S. (n.d.). *Ephraim Schröger*. archINFORM. Retrieved September 1, 2023, from
212 <https://deu.archinform.net/arch/14091.htm>
- 213 Hendel, archINFORM-S. (1719, November 2). *Georg Johann Mattarnovi*. archINFORM.
214 <https://fra.archinform.net/arch/18905.htm>

215 Jahn, P. H., Wacker, M., Welich, D., & Schlösser, S. (2016). Visualizing the Planning and Building of the
216 Dresden Zwinger. In S. Hoppe & S. Breitling (Eds.), *Virtual Palaces, Part II. Lost Palaces and their Afterlife*.
217 (Vol. 2, p. 30). PALATIUM.

218 Maiwald, F., Lehmann, C., & Lazariv, T. (2021). Fully Automated Pose Estimation of Historical Images in the
219 Context of 4D Geographic Information Systems Utilizing Machine Learning Methods. *ISPRS International*
220 *Journal of Geo-Information*, 10(11), 748. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi10110748>

221 Nicolai, B. (n.d.). *Schlüter, Andreas*. Deutsche Biographie. Retrieved September 1, 2023, from
222 <https://daten.digital-e-sammlungen.de/0001/bsb00019558/images/index.html?seite=131>

223 Passavant, G. (2001). *Wolf Caspar von Klengel: Dresden 1630-1691: Reisen, Skizzen, baukünstlerische*
224 *Tätigkeiten*. Deutscher Kunstverlag.

225 Pfeiffer, W. (1938). *Dresdner Palaisbauten des 18. Jahrhunderts* [Dissertation]. Ludwigs-Maximilians-
226 Universität München.

227 Utescher, R., Patee, A., Maiwald, F., Brusckke, J., Hoppe, S., Münster, S., Niebling, F., & Zarriß, S. (2022,
228 June). Exploring Naming Inventories for Architectural Elements for Use in Multi-modal Machine
229 Learning Applications. *COMHUM_2022*. Workshop on Computational Methods in the Humanities 2022
230 (COMHUM 2022), Lausanne. https://wp.unil.ch/llist/files/2022/06/COMHUM_2022_paper_19.pdf
231